

Going Green CAREINNOVATION 2023

Conference Program & Abstract Book

Towards a Circular Economy

8th International Symposium and Environmental Exhibition

An event to discuss future strategies, meet your clients and form strategic partnerships

May 9-11, 2023
Parkhotel Schönbrunn
Vienna, Austria

Wednesday, May 10, 2023

	Room Österreich	Room Ungarn
	Information Management (Digital Product Passport) Chair: K. Grobe, ADVA Optical Networking, DE	3R and Automated Dismantling Chair: M. Matsumoto, AIST, JP
16.30 – 18.30	<p>Circular Economy and Sustainable Product Development Case Study: A Digital Portal for product information delivery and potential for Product Digital Passport D. Poon, Cisco Systems, US</p> <p>Digital Product Passports: the key to end gadget hoarding and ensure responsibility R. Koppelaar, EcoWise Ekodenge, UK</p> <p>As less as possible and as much as necessary: WEEE recycler's information needs and technical requirements in context of the digital product passport E. Wagner, E. Poppe, M. Schneider-Ramelow, Fraunhofer IZM, DE D. Baumgärtel, M. Malzacher, I. Budde, Circular Fashion, DE</p> <p>Proof of concept for traceability of recycled gold using a blockchain-based digital product passport (DPP) F. Hänel, A. Dymek, R. Rainoldi, M. Dos Santos, iPoint-systems, DE</p> <p>Data exchange platform for a green, detectable and directly recyclable lithium-ion battery F. Hänel, M. Dos Santos, iPoint-systems, DE</p> <p>Digital Twin for Circular Economy - Literature Review and Concept Presentation J. Mügge, Fraunhofer IPK, DE</p>	<p>How did Product Value Retention Processes Perform During Supply Chain Disruption? D. Fitzsimons, European Remanufacturing Council, BE</p> <p>Mobile phone reuse businesses in Japan and an estimation of their environmental load reduction effects M. Matsumoto, AIST, JP C. Clemm, Fraunhofer IZM, DE H. Awazu, J. Tominaga, NewsedTech, JP</p> <p>Design and evaluation of a robotic unscrewing station for the non-destructive semi-automated disassembly of EoL electronics M. Piessens, M. Abdelbaky, C. Zhou, Y. Wu, B. Engelen, D. DeMarelle, J. Peeters, KU Leuven, BE</p> <p>A Cobot Based Application For PCB Disassembly L. Gandini, P. Rosa, S. Terzi, Politecnico di Milano, IT</p> <p>Computer vision based defect detection in color and depth images for electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) reuse: a case study for laptops Y. Wu, C. Zhou, W. Sterkens, M. Piessens, D. J. Diaz-Romero, W. Dewulf, J. Peeters, KU Leuven, BE</p> <p>Envisioning the potential reuse and repair of electric vehicle batteries L. Talens Peiro, M. Sanclemente Crespo, X. Gabarrell i Durany, Autonomous Univ. of Barcelona, ES M. Fervorari, M. Colledani, Politecnico di Milano, IT F. Alarte, B. Alvarez, ENVIROBAT, ES</p>
20.00	Reception by the Mayor of Vienna at the City Hall (Wappensaal, Rathaus, entrance: 1010 Vienna, Lichtenfelsgasse 2, Feststiege 2)	

Digital Product Passports: the key to end gadget hoarding and ensure responsibility

R. Koppelaar, EcoWise Ekodenge, UK

Closing the loop on Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) requires societal cultural and behaviour changes. To end the throw-away practice where 5.3 billion mobile phones are disposed of globally every year, and a multi-fold number are hoarded in drawers at home (WEEE Forum 2022). Cultural shifts include how we perceive useful end-of-use products, instead of waste as valuable resources in the language we use, and the unwritten norms agreed upon in society. And behavior changes in the daily to monthly routines we carry out around what we do with our WEEE once it is unwanted, either as we desire a product upgrade or because of product failures. A key part of the solution are Digital Product Passports as these can enable traceability up to individual product levels combined with information exchanges across product life cycle actors. Digital Product Passports make a product universally identifiable both offline and online on the internet, such that specific information can be retrieved and updated either as a product series or for each individual product. If legislated within the EU as a requirement at the individual product level, they could be rolled out universally to the 1.3 billion consumer electronic and household appliances annually placed on the EU market (Deloitte 2022). A decision to this end, whether Digital Product Passports will be legislated at individual product level is to be 27 made under the Sustainable Products Initiative of the European Commission, likely as part of delegated acts for different product categories in the 2023 to 2027 period.

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